

Internet Addiction, Self-Efficacy, and Communication Apprehension among Higher Education Students in Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

The phenomenon of growing internet usage among higher education students has introduced a new pattern of interaction, where online communication is often preferred over face-to-face interaction. This shift has led to an increase in communication apprehension, particularly among students who excessively use the internet without strong self-efficacy in situations that require direct communication. This study aims to examine the influence of internet addiction and self-efficacy on communication apprehension among higher education students. This research follows a quantitative approach with a regression design, involving 149 higher education students as the sample. To analyze the data, multiple linear regression analysis was used. The results show that both self-efficacy and internet addiction significantly impact communication apprehension, with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). The two predictor variables (self-efficacy and internet addiction) account for 30.9% ($R^2 = 0.309$) of the variance in communication apprehension. Among the two predictors, self-efficacy shows a stronger negative correlation with communication apprehension ($\beta = -0.443$) compared to internet addiction ($\beta = 0.271$).

Keywords : Internet Addiction, Self-Efficacy, and Communication Apprehension

Higher education students are the next generation expected to play a significant role in the broader societal system in the future. To fulfill this role, these students must possess the ability to engage in social interactions and have a strong sense of self-efficacy to interact effectively both interpersonally and intrapersonally. According to Bandura (1997), self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to organize and execute the actions required to achieve a specific goal. For higher education students, this includes their confidence in handling situations that require direct communication, both in interpersonal interactions and in general.

Bandura's (1997) theory of self-efficacy states that a person's belief in their ability to perform a task or succeed in a situation is a key factor influencing their performance, particularly under pressure. The concept of general self-efficacy refers to the belief that an individual can handle a variety of situations or demands (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995). This is further supported by Sherer (1982), who suggests that one's experiences of success and failure can influence their sense of self-efficacy. General self-efficacy is focused on a person's broad and stable perception of their ability to perform tasks effectively across a wide range of contexts and stressful situations (Luszczynska, 2005). Hobfoll, as described by Romadona (2017), explains that self-efficacy is the belief in one's ability to succeed in specific tasks or situations. This suggests that self-efficacy is an important characteristic for individuals to possess in order to cope with stressful events effectively. One such stressful event is experiencing anxiety in situations that require social interaction or communication.

Social interaction, according to Sudaryanto (2019), involves more than one participant, as it requires both action and reaction. It includes specific symbols used in communication, with language being the most common symbol. These symbols must be understood by all parties involved to ensure effective communication. Social interaction also has a temporal dimension, encompassing the past, present, and future. This means that every interaction occurs within a time context that defines its boundaries. The goal of the interaction determines whether it leads to cooperation or conflict. For undergraduate/graduate, mastering the components of interaction is essential as a foundation for their readiness to contribute to society.

In today's world, human interaction is increasingly inseparable from technological advancements, one of which is the internet. This technological progress has become a key factor in shaping societal life patterns. Not only does it influence the era we live in, but it also affects various aspects of life, including communication and social interaction (Mulawarman, 2020). According to a survey by APJII (2018), the largest group of internet users consists of children, adolescents, and students aged 13-18 years (75.5%), followed by late teens, young adults, and university students aged 19-34 years (74.2%). This data indicates that 7 out of 10 children, adolescents, and adults in Indonesia are internet users. In 2023, internet usage in Indonesia increased to 78.19% of the population (APJII, 2023).

Similar to the phenomenon observed among higher education students, technological advancements today undoubtedly play a significant role in daily activities, both in supporting the pursuit of knowledge and facilitating everyday social interactions. Psychologically, human behavior is an effort to meet various needs, as these needs continuously drive individuals to fulfill them. One such need is access to the internet, which serves as a source of reference for social networks, information, and various other purposes, acting as a gateway to fulfilling individual desires in accordance with the principle of dynamic efficiency (Mulawarman, 2020). Fuchs (as cited in Pratama, 2017) asserts that this situation indicates the internet has transformed from being merely a computer network into a space where humans interact and communicate.

Technological advancements do not always have a positive impact; there are also negative effects associated with internet usage. Excessive use of the internet can lead to various problems, one of which is addiction. Young (2017) defines internet addiction as the uncontrolled use of internet technology, which tends to have a harmful effect on the user. This phenomenon is also referred to as problematic internet use, pathological internet use, excessive internet use, or internet dependence (Young, 1998). Internet addiction has the potential to impair an individual's personality, and excessive internet use can lead to problems due to a lack of self-control, resulting in maladaptive pleasure derived from internet use. This is referred to as problematic internet use (Young, 2010).

The use of the internet, which has become a necessity, has further led individuals to adopt a new pattern in which social interaction through the virtual world occurs more

frequently than face-to-face interaction. Most individuals find it easier and more comfortable to interact online. Chun (as cited in Pratama, 2017) coined the popular term "new media" to refer to the social life created through human interaction via the internet. In this new media interaction pattern, individuals who have the opportunity to interact face-to-face often choose online interaction instead, due to its comfort and convenience. As a result, individuals' ability to interact and socialize in person becomes diminished.

Communication that feels more comfortable through the virtual world, without the need for face-to-face interaction, has become a new challenge for communication skills. This shift increases the likelihood of experiencing communication apprehension when individuals are required to engage in direct communication. According to Gudykunst (2002), anxiety is the underlying cause of communication failure. Anxiety affects an individual's ability to communicate effectively and adapt to new environments. McCroskey (2001) defines communication apprehension as an individual's fear or anxiety related to both the present situation and anticipated communication scenarios, whether with individuals or in social settings.

Burgoon (1976) states that communication apprehension also includes an unwillingness to communicate, which is characterized by anxiety, introversion, and low participation in various communication situations. It also involves avoiding communication due to unpleasant past experiences, as indicated by a lack of familiarity with communication situations that affect intimacy and empathy control, as well as a low level of control over communication situations caused by environmental factors. These factors include the inability to adapt to different individuals and the reactions of conversation partners. McCroskey (2001) states that most individuals feel anxious when they perceive they are being evaluated by listeners and believe that others do not experience the same anxiety when facing challenges, such as speaking in public. As a result, this experience is perceived as unique and is felt only by the individual.

Based on the explanation above, the researcher aims to investigate the extent to which self-efficacy, which is negatively correlated, influences communication apprehension experienced by higher education students. Additionally, internet addiction is assumed to have a positive correlation with communication apprehension, and this study will explore

the extent of its impact on higher education students' communication apprehension.

Research Question

The research question are as follow :

- a. Is there a negative influence of self-efficacy on communication apprehension experienced by higher education students, and a positive influence of internet addiction on communication apprehension?
- b. Which variable has a greater impact on communication apprehension among higher education students?

Research Methodology

The respondents in this study involved 149 active higher education students as the research sample, with the following demographics: 141 female respondents and 8 male respondents. Additionally, there were 118 Undergraduate (*S1*) students, 23 Graduate (*S2*) students, and 8 Diploma (*D3*) students, all of whom are active internet users for various purposes, including interaction, academic activities, and other purposes. The sampling technique used in this study was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method.

This research involves three variables, two independent variables : internet addiction and self-efficacy, and one dependent variable : communication apprehension. The study uses three measurement scales: the Internet Addiction Test (IAT), the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES), and the Communication Apprehension Inventory (CAI). The Internet Addiction Test (IAT) is adapted from Young (2017) and consists of 20 questions using a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 5. The IAT covers the full range of internet addiction symptoms, as reported by respondents, based on the following symptom patterns: salience, excessive use, neglect of work, anticipation, lack of control, and neglect of social life (Young, 1998). After testing the item discrimination power, no items were discarded in this study, with the IAT reliability coefficient of 0.904.

Self-efficacy is measured using the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES) developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995), based on Bandura's (1997) theory of self-efficacy. Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) developed a comprehensive concept of self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's overall belief in their ability to manage various demands or

situations, known as general self-efficacy. This measurement scale has been adapted into Indonesian by Novrianto (2019) and is unidimensional. It will be used in this study. The scale consists of 10 items, using a five-point Likert scale: STS (Strongly Disagree), TS (Disagree), N (Neutral), CS (Agree), and SS (Strongly Agree). After testing the item discrimination power, no items were removed from the study, with the GSES demonstrating a reliability coefficient of 0.874.

For the measurement of communication apprehension, the researcher used the Communication Anxiety Inventory (CAI) scale developed by McCroskey (1984), which has been construct-tested by Booth-Butterfield and Gould (1986). This measurement tool consists of 21 statements that describe various communication events, including: anxiety when speaking in a group, anxiety when speaking in a meeting, anxiety when speaking face-to-face with one other person, and anxiety when speaking in public. The scale uses 21 items with a four-point Likert scale: 'Almost Never', 'Sometimes', 'Often', and 'Almost Always'. After testing the item discrimination power, no items were discarded in this study, with the CAI demonstrating a reliability coefficient of 0.916.

The research design employed in this study is a quantitative correlational design, aimed at examining the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Additionally, the study seeks to assess the extent of the contribution made by the two independent variables to the dependent variable.

Data Analysis Technique

The field data were processed using SPSS IBM Data Statistics 22.0 for Windows. This data processing included normality testing, reliability testing, and linearity testing. Hypothesis testing was performed using multiple linear regression analysis, a technique applied when the study involves one dependent variable (y) and more than one independent variable (x) that influences the dependent variable (y) (Kurniawan, 2016).

Results and Discussion

Based on the descriptive analysis of communication apprehension data, the empirical mean ($x = 51.54$) is lower than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 63$), indicating that the communication apprehension experienced by students is categorized as low. For self-efficacy, the descriptive analysis shows that the empirical mean ($x = 38.55$) is higher than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 30$), suggesting that the self-efficacy levels among students are categorized as high. The descriptive analysis of internet addiction data indicates that the empirical mean ($x = 52.16$) is lower than the hypothetical mean ($\mu = 60$), which suggests that the level of internet addiction among higher education students falls within the moderate category.

The results of the mean calculations based on the respondents' educational levels show that communication apprehension experienced by higher education students across different levels of education tends to be low. However, self-efficacy and internet addiction levels among the respondents vary more significantly. The results and categories based on age are presented in Table 1

Table 1. Mean and Categories Based on Participants' Educational Levels

Level of Education	Communication Apprehension	<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	Internet Addiction
D3 (Diploma 3)	52.37 (Low)	36.25 (High)	50.25 (Medium)
S1 (Undergraduate Level)	51.96 (Low)	38.29 (High)	57.60 (Medium)
S2 (Graduate Level)	45.34 (Low)	39.73 (Very High)	38.86 (Low)

Based on the normality test for the communication apprehension variable, a p-value of 0.200 was obtained, followed by a p-value of 0.065 for internet addiction, and a p-value of 0.016 for self-efficacy. A data distribution is considered normal when the significance value is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). Therefore, both the communication apprehension and

internet addiction variables are normally distributed (symmetrical), while the self-efficacy variable is not (asymmetrical). The results of the linearity test indicate a linear relationship, with a p-value for linearity of less than 0.05, suggesting that the linear model is appropriate. Additionally, the p-value for deviation from linearity is greater than 0.05, further confirming the linear relationship.

Table 2. Results of the Regression Test for Internet Addiction, Self-efficacy, and Communication Apprehension

Predictors	Dependent Variable	R	R Square	Sig	p
Self-efficacy	Communication Apprehension	.556	.309	.000	≤ 0.05
Internet Addiction				.000	≤ 0.05

Table 3. Regression Coefficients for Internet Addiction, Self-efficacy, and Communication Apprehension

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
Constant	75.200	6.290		11.955	.000
Self-efficacy	-.881	.139	-.443	-6.354	.000
Internet Addiction	.188	.48	.271	3.881	.000

The hypothesis test was performed using multiple regression analysis. The results indicate that both self-efficacy and internet addiction have a significant effect on communication apprehension, with a significance value of .000 ($p < .05$). The coefficient of determination shows that the two predictor variables (self-efficacy and internet addiction) explain 30.9% of the variance in the criterion variable (communication apprehension), with an ($R^2 = 0.309$)

The obtained β value is -.443 for the self-efficacy variable and .271 for the internet addiction variable. This indicates that self-efficacy is negatively correlated with communication apprehension—meaning that the higher a person's self-efficacy, the lower

their communication apprehension. Conversely, internet addiction is positively correlated with communication apprehension, implying that the greater the level of internet addiction, the higher the communication apprehension experienced.

The results of this study also show that the effective contribution of each predictor variable is 21.6% for self-efficacy and 9.3% for internet addiction. This means that self-efficacy has a greater influence on communication apprehension among higher education students.

The high levels of self-efficacy observed among higher education students contribute to their low levels of communication apprehension. The data from this study indicate that higher education students at the *D3* (Diploma), *S1* (Undergraduate), and *S2* (Graduate) educational levels exhibit high and very high levels of self-efficacy, which correlate with relatively low levels of communication apprehension. These findings align with the research of Mede and Karairmak (2017), who identified a strong relationship between communication apprehension and self-efficacy. Additionally, the results suggest that students with lower self-efficacy are more likely to struggle in achieving their learning goals and tend to feel more awkward and anxious during communication.

Another notable finding in this research is that Graduate (*S2*) students exhibit a higher level of knowledge and experience, which enhances their communication performance compared to students at lower educational levels. Consequently, Graduate's students tend to have lower communication anxiety and higher levels of self-efficacy. This is also reflected in their significantly lower levels of internet addiction compared to Diploma (*D3*) and Undergraduate (*S1*) students, who show a moderate degree of internet addiction.

Furthermore, empirical mean calculations in this study revealed no instances of high internet addiction. Diploma (*D3*) and undergraduate (*S1*) students generally exhibited moderate levels of internet addiction, while graduate (*S2*) students displayed low levels. These findings align with those of Punyanunt-Carter et al. (2018), who found that communication anxiety significantly influences social media addiction. This suggests that students may favor social media for communication over face-to-face interactions. Additionally, Punyanunt-Carter et al. (2018) observed that online interactions allow individuals with face-to-face communication anxiety to exert greater control over their

environment, potentially improving their communication performance.

Based on the research data, internet addiction among Diploma (*D3*) and Undergraduate (*S1*) students is classified as moderate, while that among Graduate (*S2*) students is categorized as low. Referring to Table 3, internet addiction contributes an effective percentage of 9.3%, indicating that both moderate and low levels of internet addiction impact the communication anxiety experienced by students. This finding aligns with the study by Punyanunt-Carter et al. (2017), which indicates a relationship between participants' need to use online features and their anxiety during communication.

Based on the data presented in Table 3, respondents with a Graduate (*S2*) level of education exhibit low levels of internet addiction alongside very high self-efficacy. In contrast, Diploma (*D3*) and Undergraduate (*S1*) students demonstrate moderate levels of internet addiction and high self-efficacy. These findings align with the study by Ebrahim et al. (2022), which found that higher self-efficacy is associated with a lower tendency to experience internet addiction. Ebrahim et al. (2022) also noted that lower levels of internet addiction and higher self-efficacy correlate with greater well-being.

Conclusion and Suggestion

Based on the analysis and discussion in this study, it can be concluded that both self-efficacy and internet addiction significantly affect the communication apprehension experienced by higher education students. Self-efficacy is negatively correlated with communication apprehension, while internet addiction shows a positive correlation. The impact of self-efficacy is found to be stronger than that of internet addiction on higher education students' communication apprehension.

Based on the research findings and observations, several recommendations are made for future studies. Further research on communication apprehension could examine the anxiety levels across its specific dimensions. In addition, future studies could expand on this work by investigating other variables more closely related to internet addiction, as well as exploring its psychological impacts in greater depth. Broadening the demographic criteria to include a more diverse range of higher education students would also enhance the study, ensuring that the sample more accurately reflects the broader population.

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